

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING CONGRUENCE QUALITIES IN THE PROCESS OF PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION OF STUDENTS

Kamalova Dilobar Tairovna

Teacher of the primary education department

Shahrisabz State Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract. *Congruence qualities are full of the sincerity of the formed creative teacher. His openness is reflected in his readiness to discuss any problems with his colleagues and students, giving up "distance", establishing "safe" relationships with young people. The article also talks about the scientific importance of forming congruence qualities in future teachers.*

Keywords: *profession, congruence, ethics, education, teacher-student, knowledge, skill.*

INTRODUCTION

Congruence is conformity. This means that the teacher should be exactly what he is. In addition, he should know his attitude towards other people. It also means that he accepts his true feelings. A teacher with such a character is open in communication with his students. He can admire what he likes and get bored during conversations on topics that do not interest him. He can be angry and cold or, on the contrary, sensitive or sympathetic. Because he accepts his feelings as his own, he does not need to attribute them to his readers or demand that they feel the same way. He is not a living person, an impersonal embodiment of program requirements, or a conveyor belt for transferring knowledge. Until recently many theories of teaching took little account of the results of research on learning processes (e.g., see Duffy, Lowyck & Jonassen, 1993). In many instructional theories, the teacher is the directing agency, who prescribes to a high degree what learners should do to realize the objectives presented by the teacher. This view of teaching, which is founded on the idea that teaching essentially comes down to the transmission of knowledge from an external source to the learner, has come under increasing pressure (e.g., Biggs, 1996). Brown, Collins and Duguid (1989) notice that teaching often leads to isolated and inert knowledge. According to them, knowledge domains acquired through education are often studied in isolation from one another and are therefore difficult to access. Inertness of knowledge refers to the problem, also known in working practice, that, although pupils and students have indeed acquired a lot of knowledge, they may not have acquired the capacity to apply this knowledge to solve problems in practice. Dahlgren (1984) showed that although university students were able to talk about their field of study in more complicated words after one year of studies, their misconceptions about fundamental phenomena in that field had not changed. The speed of technological, professional and societal changes also makes it necessary for people to be able to acquire new knowledge independently after their school careers.

In response to these problems of transmission-of-knowledge teaching theories, a lively discussion has recently arisen about the presuppositions of these theories.

Teaching strategies and learning strategies are not always compatible. Between students' self-regulation and teachers' external regulation of learning processes, complex interplays may take place. *Congruence* occurs when students' learning strategies and teachers' teaching strategies

are compatible; *friction* occurs when this is not the case. The outcomes of congruence are denoted as mathemagenic effects.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHOD

From the point of view of this problem, the problem of directional proportionality is indicated. This problem can be solved if the traditional pedagogical approach to the organization of the educational process is overcome. For example, according to the systematic paradigm of education developed on the basis of Santiago's theory of knowledge, there is no problem of multidirectional actions of teachers and students. It does not appear because the teacher appears to the students in the role of researcher and not in the role of scholar and teacher. For him and for students, the subject of science is fundamentally unknown. All known scientific ideas about reality appear not as truth, but as tools of knowledge. These tools are constantly being improved by researchers, and the truth is always beyond the horizon.

The analysis of the respective course was based primarily on the student's perspective. Even though, other students may have responded differently to the questions the discussion will be based on responses from the five students who were interviewed.

DISCUSSION

He clearly understands the purpose of his existence, working in the same conditions as his colleagues, communicating with students, creating a situation for their success and development. Such teachers are an example of harmony in their profession. First, it should be noted that the result of success is always twofold. Here, it is necessary to emphasize the need-motivation coincidence (congruence) in the "teacher-student" system, that is, the desire of both sides for positive cooperation, the positive attitude of students to the goals of joint activities, adequate acceptance, solving pedagogical problems, positive attitude of students to the evaluation of the results of their activities by the teacher, adequate self-evaluation of the teacher and the student, satisfaction with the result of joint activities. The second condition is the technology of operational use of flexible and innovative forms, work methods and methods, which are determined in the previous stage and help to achieve a high level of compatibility (true mutual understanding between the teacher and the student). At this level, scientists suggest the use of such methods and methods as psychological-pedagogical diagnostics to determine the characteristics of success motivation, cognitive and emotional-volitional states. In this condition, "kindness, attention and care", "reassurance", persuasion, "advanced success", "interest awakening", emotional stimulation, conversational methods are used. This method is widely used at exhibitions, contests, fairs, excursions, parties, KVN's. The third indicator is the improvement of social well-being of students and teachers in the group. The experience of joy, satisfaction, recognition, empathic understanding will bring the student out of the negative situation in education. Here, the fact of success in one or another type of activity is an active formative principle, and real success is the key to self-realization of both the teacher and the student. Therefore, the components of the positive role of compliance are the level of motivation of the teacher to achieve success and in the team, expressed in increasing the level of self-awareness and self-affirmation in society. By improving social well-being, the teacher gains experience in self-regulation. When we always talk about teaching, we think a lot about the regular learning interactions between teachers and students in our educational activities. Within various organizational forms, in particular, in lectures, the teacher and students interact in a certain way. The attribution of such interaction is the subject of

academic science. The topic is the scientific idea of reality in that part of the world that is seen by the researcher, specialist of the relevant profile.

At a time when knowledge is getting obsolete ever faster and information is getting accessible ever easier via computer networks, the need for lifelong learning increases and teaching models based on transmission and storage of knowledge lose their functionality. Society's demand for new teaching models, aimed at developing students' ability to update their knowledge whenever necessary, is growing.

It becomes evident that the students have high expectations regarding the exam building on knowledge acquired during previous courses. Since the students feel they have an adequate acquisition of theoretical knowledge for this specific course, it is not addressed as a problem though. A clear red-thread is of importance in study programs in general as well as in the context of a single course.

RESULTS

The activity of both the teacher and students in the educational process has one subject - the subject of educational science. This fact makes it possible to note the first sign of the compatibility of the educational process - the compatibility of the subject. This indicates the special proportionality of the two activities, proportionality in the subject.

The presence of proportionality in the educational process by subject is not yet a guarantee of the complete proportionality of two types of activity, the activity of the teacher and the activity of students. The two activities may not be commensurate in focus. This happens if the teacher participates in the educational process in the capacity of "knowing and transferring knowledge to students". In this case, the teacher is closed to learning science. He knows what he knows and broadcasts it. Pupils do not know, but "learn" from the teacher. The activities of students and teachers are multifaceted. Moreover, these two activities can differ in intensity. Take, for example, a lecture. Can teacher and student situations be compared in terms of tension? As a rule, no. But probably yes. Perhaps such learning processes occur in educational practice, where both the teacher and the students are so enthusiastic about joint activities that it is no longer possible to say that the students do not work as intensively as the teacher.

Originally, we planned to evaluate student generated take home messages during a university course. Training planning builds on its own blocks; if the students lack understanding of the primary topics, they are unable to succeed in upcoming topics (tower structure). Thus, there may be a risk of misalignments between intended and actual learning outcomes. We planned for the assignment to include an investigation of an assessment tool. To do this we were to develop an evaluation tool assessing if students grasp the intended learning outcomes of each lecture. Since all lecturing was converted to on-line, as a consequence of covid19, we discussed an amendment of the project to focus on the use of the Flipped-classroom approach, as a new teaching method. Since none of our departmental supervisors were available, we had this discussion with our pedagogical supervisor. The amendment resulted in the project being as presented.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, taking into account the ratio of two types of activities in the educational process, we distinguish three types of this ratio according to parameters: accuracy, direction and intensity.

Difficulties faced by students during teacher education can range from academic problems to social and psychological aspects. Academic load, inappropriateness of teaching methods to the

individual needs of students and lack of motivation - all these can lead to difficulties in learning. Difficulties faced by students in the process of educating teachers can be overcome with the help of a systematic approach. Individualized education, psychosocial support, and teacher training are key components of successful education for all students, regardless of their individual characteristics and needs. The development of students' qualities of complexity requires the joint efforts of educational institutions, teachers and the whole society.

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